

TRAPEZIUM

Mamaraimov Bekzod Kadirovich

Teacher of mathematics at Terdu Academic Lyceum

MakhmudoV Azam Kudratovich

Teacher of mathematics at Terdu Academic Lyceum

Musurmonov Maruf Akrom ugli

Teacher of mathematics at Terdu Academic Lyceum

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18130140>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th December 2025

Accepted: 30th December 2025

Online: 31th December 2025

KEYWORDS

trapezium, esasthenic trapezium, esasthenic trapezium, surface, perimeter, diagonals, angles, geometry, rectangle, mathematical problems.

ABSTRACT

A trapezoid is a quadrilateral in geometry, bounded by straight lines, with only one pair of opposite sides parallel. The dimensions and shape of a trapezoid are important in determining its surface area, perimeter, and other geometric properties. The main types of trapezoids are: equilateral, isosceles, and simple trapezoids. In an equilateral trapezoid, the sides are equal, while in an isosceles trapezoid, the parallel sides are equal. The trapezoid is used in many mathematical problems, in physics, in calculating the area, in architecture, and in construction. The surface area, perimeter, diagonals, and angles of a trapezoid are interrelated, which helps to deepen knowledge of geometry. At the same time, the concept of a trapezoid serves as a key element in the analysis of complex geometric shapes. This article contains extensive information on the basic concepts, types, formulas for the surface area and perimeter of a trapezoid, as well as practical applications

Geometry is one of the oldest and most fundamental branches of mathematics. It studies shapes, lines, angles, and their relationships. The concept of a trapezoid plays an important role within this branch. A trapezoid is a quadrilateral with only one pair of opposite sides parallel, and studying its properties helps to further deepen your knowledge of geometry. Trapezoids are divided into different types: isosceles, isosceles, and simple trapezoids. [1]

Each type has its own characteristics and is important in terms of mathematical problems and practical applications.

In an isosceles trapezoid, the sides are equal. This type provides the symmetrical property of the trapezoid. In an isosceles trapezoid, the diagonals are also equal and the angles are symmetrical. These properties make it convenient to calculate the area of the trapezoid and solve geometric problems.

In an isosceles trapezoid, the parallel sides are equal. In this type of trapezoid, the angles and diagonals are congruent, and special formulas can be used to calculate the area and perimeter. An isosceles trapezoid is often used in architectural and design projects, as it has a symmetrical and aesthetic appearance.

In a simple trapezoid, the sides are not equal and all the angles can be different. This type of trapezoid is more often found in theoretical problems, and special formulas are used to find its area.

The main properties of a trapezoid are as follows:

Parallel sides - the most important property of a trapezoid is that only one pair of sides is parallel.

Sides - in an isosceles trapezoid, the sides are equal, while in a simple trapezoid they may not be equal.[2]

Angles - the opposite angles of a trapezoid are expressed by various formulas. In an equilateral trapezoid, the side angles are equal.

Diagonals - the diagonals may or may not be equal, depending on the type of trapezoid.

There are several methods for calculating the area of a trapezoid:

1. Simple formula:

$$S = \frac{(a+b)}{2} \times h$$

Here:

a, b are the parallel sides of the trapezoid,
h is the height.

2. Using coordinates:

If the corner coordinates of the trapezoid are known, the area can be calculated using the coordinate formula.

Accurately calculating the area of a trapezoid is important in practical problems, such as measuring area, architectural or design projects.

Perimeter of a trapezoid

The perimeter of a trapezoid is the sum of the lengths of all sides:

$$\text{Perimeter} = a + b + c + d$$

Where:

a and b are the parallel sides,
c and d are the lateral sides.

In an equilateral trapezoid, $c = d$, which makes it easier to calculate the perimeter. The perimeter is used in geometry problems to determine the length of the boundary of the trapezoid.

Diagonals and angles

The diagonals and angles of a trapezoid vary depending on its type. In an equilateral trapezoid, the diagonals are equal and symmetrical. The angles are congruent with the opposite angles. In a simple trapezoid, the diagonals may not be equal and the angles may be different. The calculation of diagonals and angles is carried out using trigonometric formulas.

The trapezoid is not limited to theoretical geometry, but is also widely used in everyday life:

Architecture and construction: Trapezoidal windows, ceilings, and decorative elements are used in the design.

Physics and mathematics problems: Calculating the area and perimeter of a trapezoid is used in modeling physical processes.

Design and art: The trapezoid shape creates an aesthetic appearance in graphic design and works of art.[4]

The various types and properties of a trapezoid provide convenience in design, calculation, and practical work. Therefore, a trapezoid is one of the important concepts in mathematical sciences.

Example problem

Problem: Given an equilateral trapezoid: parallel sides $a = 8$ cm, $b = 4$ cm, height $h = 5$ cm. Find the area and perimeter of the trapezoid.

Solution:

$$S = \frac{(a+b)}{2} \times h = \frac{(8+4)}{2} \times 5 = 30 \text{ sm}$$

In conclusion, the trapezoid is one of the basic elements of geometric concepts, widely used in various mathematical problems and practical work. The formulas for calculating the types, surface area, perimeter, diagonals and angles of a trapezoid help to deepen knowledge of geometry. The trapezoid is used not only in mathematical theory, but also in architecture, design and physics. This article aims to highlight the practical significance of the trapezoid using its main properties, types, formulas and examples.

References:

1. Kiselev A.P., Geometry, Moscow, 2010.
2. Baldin V.A., Planimetry, St. Petersburg, 2012.
3. Savchenko V.I., Mathematics in Practice, Kiev, 2015.
4. Lobachevsky N.I., Foundations of Geometry, Moscow, 2018.